

Alkali Sulphonates of Coumarin and Nitrocoumarin.

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Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1873, **24**, 37) sulphonated coumarin with fuming sulphuric acid and obtained mono-sulphonic acid of coumarin (sulphocoumarilic acid) at the temperature of water-bath, and the disulphonic acid (disulphocoumarilic acid) at 150°; but he did not determine the position of the sulphonic acid groups. The object of the present paper is to study further the sulphonation of coumarin and nitrocoumarin with a view to determine the constitution of these sulphonic acids and also to prepare their simple derivatives such as the sulphochlorides and the sulphonamides.

The mono-sulphonic acid of coumarin has been prepared by the action of ordinary fuming sulphuric acid on coumarin on the water-bath and the disulphonic acid and nitrocoumarin monosulphonic acid have been obtained by the action of fuming sulphuric acid on coumarin and nitrocoumarin respectively at 150°. The laborious method of isolation of the sulphonic acids of coumarin followed by Perkin by means of their barium salts has been replaced by the salting out process with advantage, whereby they are readily obtained in good yields as their sodium salts. The yield of the disulphonic acid of coumarin is much greater with 50% fuming sulphuric acid than with ordinary fuming acid used by Perkin.

The usual methods for the determination of the position of the sulphonic acid groups in simpler aromatic compounds by the replacement of the sulphonic acid group by hydroxyl group by alkali-fusion or by nitro group (*J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 2039) or halogen atoms (*ibid*, page 2028) have not been successful in the case of the sulphonic acids of coumarin the alkali fusion leading to a rupture of the lactonic ring of the coumarin molecule.

The constitution of these acids has therefore been determined by oxidising the lactonic ring with alkaline potassium permanganate solution and obtaining from each of them known derivatives of salicylic acid. Thus the oxidation product of the mono-sulphonic acid of coumarin or sulpho-coumarilic acid of Perkin melts at 113°;

the desiccated product shrinks above 115° , and decomposes at about 178° and has therefore been identified with 5-sulpho-salicylic acid (Meldrum and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1989) proving it to be coumarin-6-sulphonic acid (I).

It has been shewn by Clayton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97 1397) that when 6-nitrocoumarin is further nitrated, the second nitro group enters the lactonic ring in preference to the benzenoid ring and this peculiar susceptibility of the lactonic ring has also been observed in the case of sulphonation. Thus 6-nitrocoumarin-sulphonic acid gives on oxidation 5 nitrosalicylic acid (m. p. 228°), shewing that the SO₃H group has entered the lactone ring. Similarly in the case of the disulphonic acid of coumarin, the second sulphonic acid group enters the lactone ring as the oxidation product (5-sulphosalicylic acid) contains only one sulphonic acid group.

It has been definitely proved by Clayton (*loc. cit.*) that the nitration product of 6-nitrocoumarin is 3:6-dinitrocoumarin and from analogy it seems reasonable to suppose that the SO₃H group entering the lactonic ring like the nitro group occupies the position 3, and hence the disulphonic acid of coumarin or the disulpho-coumarilic acid of Perkin is presumably coumarin 3:6-disulphonic acid (II) and the nitro-coumarin sulphonic acid is coumarin-6-nitro-3-sulphonic acid (III).

These sulphonic acids, readily isolated as their sodium salts by salting out, yield with PCl₅ or POCl₃ sulphochlorides, which in their turn give sulphonamides and sulphonanilides on usual treatment with ammonium carbonate and aniline. These sulphochlorides and sulphonamides are crystalline substances with definite melting points.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sodium salt of Coumarin-6-sulphonic Acid.—Coumarin (10 g.) and ordinary fuming sulphuric acid (50 g.) are heated on the boiling water-bath for two hours and the cold solution is filtered into

saturated brine and on keeping for a day or two the whole mass solidifies. The solution is filtered off and the residue washed with brine and finally crystallised from water (yield 85 %).

It forms thin silky needles, readily soluble in water and sparingly soluble in alcohol. (Found: S, 12·6, 12·65. $C_9H_6O_5SNa$ requires S, 12·9 per cent.).

Coumarin-6-sulphochloride.—The above sodium salt is mixed with PCl_5 or $POCl_3$ and heated on the water-bath for an hour. The mixture is poured into ice and filtered. The residue is washed with water and extracted with ether. Crystalline solid, soluble in ether and chloroform; m. p. 115°. (Found: S, 13·05. $C_9H_5O_5SCl$ requires S, 13·1 per cent.).

Coumarin-6-sulphonamide.—The sulphochloride is thoroughly mixed with excess of ammonium carbonate and heated on the water-bath for about 2 hours. The mixture is then washed with water and the residue crystallised from water. Needle-shaped crystals, soluble in alcohol and boiling water; m. p. 186°. (Found: S, 14·0; N, 6·3. $C_9H_7O_5SN$ requires S, 14·2; N, 6·2 per cent.).

Sulphonanilide.—The sulphochloride is dissolved in hot aniline and the solution heated on the water-bath for a few minutes. The solution is then poured into acid water, when the anilide is precipitated. It is filtered, washed with acid water and finally crystallised from dilute alcohol. Needle-shaped crystalline solid, insoluble in water and easily soluble in alcohol; m. p. 132°. (Found: S, 10·68; N, 4·8. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5SN$ requires S, 10·6; N, 4·6 per cent.).

Oxidation of Sodium Salt of Coumarin-6-sulphonic Acid.—Five gm. of the substance are dissolved in 2N-KOH and a 4 per cent. solution of potassium permanganate is added drop by drop to the alkaline solution cooled to 0° till the oxidation is complete. The solution is then heated for about an hour on the water-bath and then filtered from the thick mud of precipitated manganese dioxide. The filtrate is then concentrated on the water-bath and conc. HCl added, when crystals of the acid potassium salt of 5-sulphosalicylic acid separate. These are filtered off and recrystallised from water. (Found: S, 12·8; K, 15·4. $C_7H_5O_5SK$ requires S, 12·5; K, 15·2 per cent.).

The acid potassium salt is dissolved in dilute alcohol and barium chloride solution is added to it, when barium salt of 5-sulphosalicylic

cyclic acid separates. This is filtered off, dissolved in water, and decomposed with theoretical quantity of sulphuric acid, and the solution, after being filtered off from the precipitated barium sulphate, is concentrated on the water-bath and left in a desiccator overnight, when crystals of 5-sulphosalicylic acid separate. Recrystallised from water, the product melts at 113° , shrinks from about 115° and decomposes at about 178° .

Disodium Salt of Coumarin-3:6-disulphonic Acid.—Ten gms. of coumarin and 70 gms. of 50% fuming sulphuric acid are heated on an oil-bath at 150° for three to four hours and the cold solution is filtered into saturated brine, when the mass solidifies all at once. The solution is filtered off and the residue, containing a mixture of the mono- and di-sulphonic acids of coumarin, is thoroughly washed with brine and crystallised three or four times from water, when the more soluble salt of mono-sulphonic acid remains in solution and the less soluble salt of the disulphonic acid is obtained in the pure state (yield—07 per cent.).

Silky needles, moderately soluble in water and almost insoluble in alcohol. (Found: S, 17.9, 18.0. $C_9H_6O_6S_2Na_2$ requires S, 18.3 per cent.).

Disulpho-dichloride.—Prepared as in the case of mono-sulphochloride. Needle-shaped crystals, soluble in ether and benzene, moderately soluble in alcohol and insoluble in water; m. p. 170° - 173° . (Found: S, 18.65. $C_9H_4O_6S_2Cl_2$ requires S, 18.7 per cent.).

Disulphon-diamide.—Prepared as in the case of mono-sulphonamide and is crystallised from water. Needle-shaped crystals, soluble in ether and alcohol and somewhat soluble in water, m. p. above 240° . (Found: N, 9.15. $C_9H_6O_6S_2N_2$ requires N, 9.2 per cent.).

Di-sulphondianilide.—Prepared as in the case of the mono-sulphonanilide and is crystallised from dilute alcohol. Yellow crystals soluble in alcohol and is insoluble in water. (Found: N, 6.1. $C_{21}H_{14}O_6S_2N_2$ requires N, 6.1 per cent.).

Oxidation of Coumarin-3:6-disulphonic Acid.—The process of oxidation is the same as in the case of the mono-sulphonic acid and the acid potassium salt of 5-sulphosalicylic acid is obtained in good

yield. (Found: S, 12.9 ; K, 15.3. $C_7H_6O_6SK$ requires S, 12.5 ; K, 15.2 per cent.).

Sodium salt of Coumarin-6-nitro-3-sulphonic Acid.—Ten gms. of 6-nitrocoumarin and 60 gms. of 50% fuming sulphuric acid are heated on the oil-bath at 150° for three to four hours and the cold solution is filtered into saturated brine, when crystals of the sodium salt separate. These are filtered off, washed with brine and recrystallised from water (yield—80 per cent.).

Long yellowish needles, moderately soluble in alcohol and easily soluble in water. (Found: S, 10.7 ; N, 4.85. $C_6H_4O_6SNNa$ requires S, 10.9 ; N, 4.8 per cent.).

The *sulphochloride* was prepared as in the case of the mono-sulphochloride and then crystallised from benzene. Crystalline solid, readily soluble in alcohol, moderately soluble in benzene and almost insoluble in ether ; m. p. 205°. (Found: S, 11.2 ; N, 4.8. $C_6H_4O_6SNCl$ requires S, 11.1 ; N, 4.8 per cent.).

Sulphonamide.—Prepared as in the case of the mono-sulphonamide and is then crystallised from water. Needle-shaped crystals, readily soluble in alcohol and boiling water. Does not melt up to 260°. (Found: N, 10.2. $C_6H_4O_6SN_2$ requires N, 10.4 per cent.).

Sulphonanilide.—Prepared as in the case of the mono-sulphonanilide and then crystallised from alcohol. Crystalline solid, soluble in alcohol and insoluble in water ; m. p. 130°. (Found: N, 8.3. $C_{11}H_{10}O_6SN_2$ requires N, 8.1 per cent.).

Oxidation of Coumarin-6-nitro-3-sulphonic Acid.—The process of oxidation is the same as in the case of the mono- and di-sulphonic acids. Conc. hydrochloric acid when added to the concentrated alkaline solution after the removal of the precipitated manganese dioxide throws down crystals of 5-nitrosalicylic acid. The product, after recrystallisation from water, melts at 228°.

